

AI-driven Framework for Scalable Management of Network Slices

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Abstract—This paper describes a scalable solution for orchestrating and managing a massive number of network slices that leverages Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques to design robust and sustainable networks. To achieve this goal, the proposed approach decomposes the management and orchestration (M&O) plane using separation of concerns and uses AI techniques to automate M&O operations. The M&O automation is achieved through the use of multiple, distributed and AI-driven control loops. The control loops have different goals and may work on the node level, slice level, inter-slice level or orchestration domain level. We also present a case study of using the proposed distributed intelligent components to scale, optimize and improve the network infrastructure. Finally, we briefly describe some challenges and future directions for scalable M&O on the road to 6G.

Index Terms—scalable, network management, orchestration, 6G, robust, requirements.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Sixth Generation (6G) is considered a “shift” toward a new era of scalable and intelligent connectivity. Considering the factors of sustainability, security, and a distributed Artificial Intelligence (AI)-native architecture, 6G networks must also be scalable, energy-efficient, and trustworthy to meet the diverse needs of users and operators [1], specifically supporting “convergence” of digital, physical, and personal domains. One key technology in future mobile and fixed networks is network slicing. It enables the deployment of isolated virtual environments for building virtual networks or services. The original idea [2] has gained considerable popularity as the subject of numerous research projects and standardization efforts and is included in the 5G Standalone (SA) variant [3]. The 5G uses European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) Network Function Virtualization (NFV) Management and Orchestration (MANO) [4] framework for the deployment of Network Slices (NSs).

The approach uses a common management plane for all NSs (a common Operations and Business Support System – OSS/BSS), which raises several issues. First, a single OSS/BSS reduces isolation between slices, also making access

of NS owners and/or operators (e.g., verticals, typically called tenants) problematic. Such an approach raises scalability and resilience issues (e.g., it represents a single point of failure and causes high monitoring overhead [1]). Moreover, modification of OSS/BSS (typically required for each deployed slice since each function of NS requires a management counterpart) is not described in the 3GPP specifications. Finally, the described approach is over-complex, as the separation of concerns is not foreseen in the OSS/BSS.

This paper presents a network management framework for 6G networks to cope with the scalability of NS management and improve management performance (compared to traditional approaches, e.g., centralized MANO [5]). Whereas the problem of user and control plane performance of mobile networks has been addressed by Standards Development Organizations (SDOs), the Management and Orchestration (M&O) still lacks Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). However, performance affects, for example, response time to faults, resource allocation efficiency, and NSs lifecycle and runtime management. With a massive number of slices, the M&O can be a bottleneck that affects the performance of the entire system. To address the M&O performance problem, we defined an architecture in which programmable M&O operations are distributed and enable fast local M&O actions. We incorporated several feedback loop-based operations targeting different goals and ranges (from fast local to slow global). These loops typically use AI algorithms. The proposed M&O plane decomposition is based on the separation of concerns (dedicated M&O for each network slice, resources, etc.). Such decomposition, combined with the use of AI and declarative policies (intents), reduces the amount of information exchanged between M&O subsystems. The approach, which enables “self-x” features and governed by high-level policies, can potentially support a large number of operations with marginal human intervention.

In particular, we consider *i*) a distributed but hierarchical network slicing system management plane *ii*) slice management embedded into NS template, *iii*) a programmable management plane *iv*) automated management and orchestration functionalities exploiting AI/Machine Learning (ML) as in 6G networks, where the AI-driven approach shall be part of the architectural design [6]. In the following sections, we first present a general vision and architecture of a scalable M&O platform and extend it with algorithmic frameworks to build a 6G roadmap in terms of scalability, robustness, automation, security/privacy, and sustainability. Later, we list the main

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challenges encountered when moving from centralized M&O to a distributed approach and present the case study of scaling NS with the proposed platform. Finally, we provide future directions and draw conclusions.

II. MONB5G FRAMEWORK

The ETSI Zero-touch network & Service Management (ZSM) group has defined a comprehensive list of requirements for zero-touch management that includes over 170 topics related to autonomous management [7]. The MonB5G project [8] addresses many of them. The main feature of the MonB5G framework is the decomposition of the management system into a set of cooperating/federated and autonomous AI-driven distributed management subsystems (see Fig.1). Each of the M&O subsystems is focused on a specific goal. Such an approach fits well with the multi-provider/multi-operator virtualization ecosystem (see Fig.2).

Fig. 1. Vision of the MonB5G project. The yellow blocks show distributed management plane. A single domain case.

The proposed approach is distributed but hierarchical. At the highest level of the management hierarchy, there is a Master OSS/BSS (MOSS) which consists of the Inter-Domain Manager and Orchestrator (IDMO) and System Portal (SP). The MOSS is responsible for the overall management, the IDMO is responsible for interdomain operations (e.g., connectivity setup between domains), while the SP is the portal used by various business stakeholders, slice tenants, slice management providers, and the system operator. The SP also interacts with IDMO, Slice OSS/BSSs (SOSSs). Each orchestration domain is, in turn, managed by Domain Manager and Orchestrator (DMO). The DMO is defined to be agnostic to the orchestrated NSs, focusing solely on resource allocation (slice admission, etc.). It can be considered a resource orchestrator enhanced by a management part responsible for orchestrating Fault, Configuration, Accounting, Performance and Security (FCAPS). In the concept, there are also Infrastructure OSS/BSSs (IOSSs) responsible for the management of the infrastructure, typically operated by the cloud provider and focuses on the reliable and energy- and cost-efficient resources provisioning to DMO.

The SOSS is a part of each NS template; therefore, it is not a permanent M&O entity. Implementing SOSS as part of a slice (i.e., a set of virtual functions) enables the use of resource scaling to improve the performance of SOSS. This mechanism is not present in the 3GPP approach. The SOSS is responsible for slice-specific management, runtime orchestration and can send orchestration requests to the DMO. It uses multiple feedback loops to handle slice FCAPS. Such operations are supported by self-managed NS functions which have a feedback loop driven Embedded Element Manager (EEM). The EEM scope of management is only its function. Such a decomposition reduces the amount of management information exchanged within a slice and reduces management reaction time. In the case of the end-to-end network slice, consisting of several subnetwork slices, a dedicated component called Inter-Domain Slice Manager (IDSIM) is added to one of them to manage the entire slice chain (see Fig. 2). Logically, it is above SOSS in the management hierarchy, but for simplicity, it is integrated with one of SOSSs. IDSIM is part of one of the slice templates composing the end-to-end network slice.

All the management subsystems and entities mentioned above interact to achieve the overall management objectives. The mentioned decomposition contributes to NS M&O scalability - each OSS has a different scope, and the raw data exchange between OSSs is minimized as many analyses and decisions are made locally. We assume that such information exchange is used for KPIs, alerts, and policy-based management implemented with declarative policies (intents). Note that there should be no information exchange between SOSSs unless they are managing parts of an end-to-end slice. DMO and IOSS are involved in the runtime NS orchestration that performs resource allocation or function placement, but they are not involved in the NS runtime management, which is the task of SOSS. However, the key technology that contributes to M&O scalability is automation. Such automation is usually based on multiple control loops that implement feedback-based adaptive management. It has been noted that the use of multi-objective optimization poses many problems in managing networks; therefore, typically, each of the management loops has a specific, single management objective. This, in turn, raises the issue of loops coordination.

A generic control loop consists of a Monitoring System (MS), one or more instances of Analytical Engines (AEs), a Decision Engine (DE), and an Actuator (ACT) that interact via message buses. The MS is responsible for monitoring, KPIs calculation and collection of events from relevant components of the NS or a "domain" (Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) and Physical Network Functions (PNFs)). The AE receives the monitoring information, processes the data, and provides the required analysis results to the DE. It may perform time-series predictions and feature space regressions, clustering, and classification to gain insights from measurements collected by MS. The DE uses a predefined policy or is AI-driven to decide which action to apply (resource allocation change, NS configuration parameters modification, or adding a new function). A DE may also control the MS measurement granularity or the AE prediction parameters. In general, a DE can change the configuration parameters of the other components with which

Fig. 2. Multi-domain architecture in a multi-provider environment.

it interacts. In the proposed framework, the output of multiple DEs is translated into lower-level orders by the ACTs.

Each OSS of the framework can accommodate multiple orchestrated control loops designed and developed for specific goals. However, it is assumed that the MS of each OSS is common for all control loops of each domain and that DEs are typically driven by AI/ML algorithms. These types of algorithms are commonly used to implement AEs and can also be used to support MS, e.g., for adaptive monitoring.

Fig. 3. High-level view of the internal structure of Slice OSS (example with multiple message buses).

Since the key component of the framework is SOSS, we will provide more details on its reference implementation. A simplified, generic SOSS structure is shown in Fig. 3. Each virtual function of NS has embedded management functions whose scope is limited to that virtual function only. We refer to this component as EEM. The EEM can be implemented with

multiple control loops targeting VNF-level optimization. At the higher level of the NS management hierarchy, there is a SOSS that interacts with all EEMs of its NS. The SOSS can use multiple control loops, but it is proposed to decompose them into MS, AE, DE, and ACT layers. Such decomposition enables the programmability of the individual layers by updating, replacing, adding, or removing layer components. The framework proposes the use of message buses for interaction between OSS components, and Fig. 3 shows how multiple message buses can be used. The DEs of the SOSS can change the configuration of existing components of the managed NS, but they can also be involved in data-driven (proactive) runtime orchestration - resource scaling or adding or removing VNFs to a slice. These functions can be part of the User Plane (e.g., deep packet inspection), the Control Plane, or the SOSS (i.e., the Management Plane). Therefore, SOSS can act as a service orchestrator providing a new feature – programmability of the Management Plane of NS. SOSS (or IDSM) enables direct interaction with the slice tenant by providing a direct management interface that is expected to be intent-driven. In the event that the tenant is not interested in NS management, another entity, the slice management provider, can assume this role (c.f. Fig.2). The entity using a dedicated version of SOSS can manage multiple NSs instantiated with the same template. Such an approach reduces the NS template footprint and accelerates its deployment.

III. ROLE OF AI IN 6G MANAGEMENT AND ORCHESTRATION

AI-driven enablers will play a key role in emerging 6G networks by facilitating zero touch M&O, increasing network robustness, improving network scalability, leveraging security and privacy mechanisms, and contributing to the sustainability of network operations. The 6G network components can leverage several AI-driven techniques to improve performance monitoring of NSs (usage of novel KPIs), decision making (e.g., by multi-agent Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) [9]), to improve KPI prediction (e.g., graph-based learning) or distributed analytics to achieve low Service Level Agreement (SLA) violations (e.g., Federated Learning (FL)), identify, detect and mitigate attacks on 6G network components, etc. The Mon5G project provides multiple solutions that, using the aforementioned architecture, contribute to the 6G targets, as described below.

A. Scalability

Decentralized management and operations are critical to meet the scalability requirements of slice-aware mobile network infrastructure [10]. Therefore, distributed AI techniques such as FL, Federated Deep Reinforcement Learnings (FDRLs) can play a crucial role in this case, enabling local processing of management data and reducing data interchange between system entities, while improving data privacy.

The distributed nature of Radio Access Network (RAN) deployments and the embedded uncertainty in resource allocation tasks introduced by variable wireless channels, user mobility, and unpredictable end-user demand make RAN management

difficult. To address this problem, a FDRL mechanism can be used to manage network slice resources in a distributed way. In the approach agents adjust resource allocation to reflect the long-term characteristics of the underlying network traffic. This mechanism can make traffic-aware local decisions that leverage both local monitoring information and global knowledge [9]. FDRL enables information exchange among local agents, which in turn not only learn from a local (and limited) observation of traffic dynamics but also benefit from the experience of other (statistically different) RAN nodes, leading to an improvement in both generalization and convergence of the learning process.

B. Automation

AI techniques, such as deep learning or DRL, are suitable for use in highly heterogeneous environments that generate large management datasets. In future mobile networks, M&O operations must flexibly adapt to dynamically changing and distributed network environments. In this sense, we applied DRL to increase scalability with network slice placement automation, considering a multi-criteria optimization approach to the problem. Heuristically Assisted Deep Reinforcement Learning (HA-DRL) solutions in MonB5G delivered 90% slice acceptance ratio even under high 90% network load [11]. Another novel DRL-based approach applied in MonB5G uses knowledge of daily enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) traffic variations to make slice admission decisions that maximize resource utilization and increase actual resource utilization by more than 20% compared to traditional DRL methods.

C. Security and Privacy

Improving resiliency and robustness to security threats across communications is vital for next-generation 6G networks. Secure and trustworthy deployment and management of cross-domain network slices are achieved through security and trust modeling. Furthermore, this can also be achieved through management approaches such as blockchain networks or ML algorithms that are designed for challenging security tasks such as aLTER attacks [12], in slice massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC) attacks [13], and poisoning attacks when training a FL model (the reference 5G datasets were collected from the MonB5G testbeds to accelerate future research on this topic) [14]. Moreover, the cloud-native implementation of the MonB5G framework leverages scalability and integration at different management levels (slice, node, orchestration domain) for different scenarios such as Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) attacks [13].

D. Robustness

Predictive analytic approaches (e.g., graph representation techniques such as Graph Neural Network (GNN)) that build on MonB5G's closed-loop control management philosophy can help reduce faults and response times. GNNs are a class of deep learning methods designed to perform inference on data described by graphs. The use of the graph provides prediction tasks at the node, edge, and graph levels, and

also incorporates the features of the node neighbors into the learning, which increases accuracy. To represent all network features for large networks, we also used Graph Convolutional Network (GCN). GCN can capture the structural information of graphs, such as the relationships between nodes and their connectivity patterns.

Fig. 4. G5IAD framework designed to detect anomalies.

A combination of GCN and recurrent connections, called Graph-based Interpretable Anomaly Detection (G5IAD), was developed to capture both spatial and temporal relationships between network attributes in a network slice for anomaly detection [15]. The proposed framework receives as input multiple time series representing the slice KPIs such as bandwidth, CPU, RAM, storage, etc and detects anomalies in slice latency. The sequences for the input model, as shown in Fig. 4, are passed through the Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) layers, while the correlation matrices are processed by GCNs. We first use the historical time series data as input, and the GCN is used to capture the topological structure of the network and obtain the relational dependencies. Second, the obtained time series with relational dependencies are input into the gated recurrent units, where the units capture the temporal features. Finally, we obtain the results through the fully connected layer to predict the slice KPIs. After prediction, Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) techniques are used to improve transparency in AI-based decision-making processes, enhancing operators' understanding. By analyzing network performance data, XAI identifies patterns and anomalies, aiding in faster fault diagnosis and correction by providing explanations through the interpretability framework.

E. Sustainability

Sustainability is one of the most important goals for future 6G networks, which should make optimal use of available infrastructure resources and maximize energy efficiency. The MonB5G architecture offers several features that can contribute to network energy efficiency. These include automated and data-driven network management for resource consumption estimates and resource groupings to maximize resource utilization, or specialized KPIs to measure OPEX savings and reduce managerial overhead through zero-touch slice MANO. Advanced SOSS with AI-driven AE/DE capabilities for greater flexibility and robustness, together with real-time monitoring

of MS, enable efficient and dynamic resource allocation. The system distribution is suitable for accommodating FL-based AEs, making real-time data analysis and prediction much more energy-efficient. The Statistical Federated Learning (StFL) approach presented in Section V aims to minimize overhead but can also save energy. DEs implement cross-domain energy-aware VNF and Service Function Chaining (SFC) deployment in 5G/6G service-tailored network slices using decentralized DRL techniques. A cross-domain reconfiguration is performed when the assignment becomes too complex and the local information is insufficient.

IV. MAJOR CHALLENGES

A. Orchestration in distributed domains

Decomposing the central management and orchestration system into distributed and modular closed-loop management and orchestration subsystems needs a suitable mapping structure for multiple technology and administrative domains. For example, the RAN needs to be mapped with some degree of coupling between the edge network and the cloud network domain such that emerging AI algorithms can be easily connected with predefined standards. A new approach is needed that combines all aspects of distributed, AI-powered management algorithms while enabling the interdependency and composition of multiple smaller subsystems required to manage the underlying complex and heterogeneous infrastructure with diverse service requirements and a growing number of network slices. One solution is to use dependency semantics to enable the composition of such a complex network of interconnected algorithms, each with its own management domain.

B. Coordination in Decentralized Systems

Distributed architectures appear to require extensive coordination and synchronization at both the slice and domain levels, which can result in significant overhead. However, this problem can be effectively addressed through the use of AI-driven analysis and decision strategies such as FL, multi-agent, and federated DRL. By prioritizing the exchange of parameters rather than raw data and minimizing both the frequency of synchronization and escalation of local optimization tasks to either the domain or end-to-end MANO systems, this challenge can be mitigated.

C. AI Performance and Cost

Training large-scale models poses multiple system challenges in terms of network, storage, and computing. To support multi-node distributed training, MonB5G has leveraged frameworks and algorithms (e.g., cloud-native implementation of distributed intelligence components with the Kubernetes (K8s) environment, use of FL, graph-based learning, DRL) that support training in large computing clusters. To further improve modeling performance for 6G use cases, training datasets can be precomputed, preprocessing steps can be offloaded to multiple Central Processing Unit (CPU) instances, model operators within the frameworks can be optimized, and high-performance storage systems can be used.

V. CASE STUDY: SCALING NETWORK SLICES USING THE MONB5G FRAMEWORK

In this section, we demonstrate the use of the proposed scalable MANO framework through the case study of the *StFL approach*, which is described in detail in [10]. We also consider an additional baseline, namely, a fully centralized SLA-constrained deep learning (CCL) model that is trained on the full dataset composed of the aggregation of each of the client's mini-datasets as given in Fig. 5 with corresponding steps. Both StFL and CCL are tuned to keep the same level of SLA violation constraints. A SLA is established between slice tenant and infrastructure provider so that the CPU resources must lie within a given interval under a probability threshold during the learning process. The StFL framework is implemented with Docker containers acting as clients and an aggregation Kubernetes server to orchestrate the distributed intelligence components.

Fig. 5. Execution steps for StFL - training for each round and CCL.

According to the flowchart in Fig. 5 that describes StFL, in Step 1, all clients (in this case, technology domains) are registered to the aggregation server. Then, the StFL training process starts in Step 2 with the registered clients. In Step 3, local training is performed in predicting the resource utilization (e.g., CPU utilization of Virtual Baseband Unit (vBBU) in our case) considering the SLA violation constraints. The TensorFlow Constrained Optimization (TFCO) library is used to solve the optimization problem. In Step 4, the model weights of the local clients are sent to the aggregation server and in Step 5, the model weights of the clients are averaged. The updated weights are sent back to all clients. Finally, the same process is repeated for the remaining FL rounds, starting from Step 3.

A. Analysis for Scalable Networks

Fig. 6 shows a comparison of the overhead between centralized and distributed management with StFL when the number of slices increases from 3 to 90. The approximate overhead between the AEs and the aggregation server can be calculated as the multiplication of FL rounds (21 rounds where convergence occurs when SLA violation reaches 1% and loss variation is small), number of AEs, number of weights of the neural network model and encoding bits of each weight

(32 bits is assumed). Since it was not possible to form a large number of slices, in our approach, we started with a sample dataset belonging to three different slices and then randomly selected new data samples of the same size to form new additional slices until we reached 90 slices. Note that the convergence time is almost independent of the number of slices since the dataset is the same size for each slice, and the management is done within the slices.

Fig. 6. Overhead comparisons of centralized versus distributed management with StFL as a function of increasing number of slices.

A CCL solution leads to overhead costs that increases significantly with the number of slices. For example, for a dataset with a size of 1875 KB, deploying a set of 15 network slices with an average of 20 Base Stations (BSs) per slice (with a separate MS and AE involved in the FL process for each BS) results in an overhead of 9375 KB. Therefore, deploying a network service with 90 slices would require an overhead of about 56250 KB (a 30-fold increase over the original data size). On the other hand, for a similar configuration, StFL incurs an overhead of only about 63 KB for 15 network slices and 414 KB for 90 network slices (4.5-fold reduction compared to the original data size). Therefore, a distributed management approach as proposed in this paper might be more beneficial for operators and service providers.

VI. FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Some of the problems faced in our experimental analysis and future research directions can be summarized as follows:

(i) There is a need of standardization of a M&O performance. This includes the definition of benchmarks and baseline solutions.

(ii) Applying Digital Twin (DT) to network management enhances intelligence, automation, and predictability, providing better-managed network services through the integration of network state, AI models, control loop execution, and historical data. DT can be well combined with XAI to increase operator confidence in AI-based solutions.

(iii) AI security is an important issue that has to be addressed yet. It concerns issues with AI algorithms security and data security and privacy.

(iv) Application agnostic control loops in large and heterogeneous domains require further work. Most of the existing solutions rely on application-specific pipeline triggering

approaches (e.g., a tactile Internet or haptic communication application requires separate pipeline components and fine-tuning in containerized environments), and more general approaches to triggering the orchestration of distributed components may be needed.

(v) Several control-loop pipelines developed independently have the potential to create unavoidable inconsistencies or conflicts. Some potential solutions could be deploying relevant conflict resolution algorithms or hierarchical closed-loop control solutions.

(vi) Further evaluations in massive scaling scenarios on benefits of distributed solutions relying on FL models need to be investigated especially from the point of view of benefit versus the cost of training large scale models (requiring a high degree of parameters and convergence rounds).

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we studied an AI-driven scalable M&O framework for the 6G vision. In doing so, we highlighted its potential to revolutionize the way network slices are managed at scale and presented some of its unique challenges. The approach provides performance improvements, isolation of the management planes of slices by design, M&O plane programmability, and reduces information exchanged between (and within) different “domains”. This has been achieved due to separation of concerns, NS-agnostic orchestration and local management information processing empowered by AI. In this approach, the provisioning of a slice requires a minor change to Operational Support System (OSS)/Business Support System (BSS) to support the runtime management of each slice and the feature can be used in 6G networks composed dynamically. We also presented a case study of building a scalable M&O platform that can accommodate a large number of network slices while keeping the SLA violations below certain thresholds. The approach presented also fits well with future infrastructure enhancements, such as improving ubiquitous connectivity with satellite-based communications networks or renewable energy resources towards 6G.

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